

A SIMPLE GUIDE FOR DESIGNING A PHOTOVOLTAIC AND BATTERY SYSTEM COUPLED WITH A HEAT PUMP ACROSS EUROPE

Mattia Dallapiccola, Jennifer Adami, David Moser
Eurac Research, Institute for Renewable Energy
Via A.Volta, 13/A, 39100, Bolzano

ABSTRACT:

The aim of this work is to provide a guide for the design of a photovoltaic plus battery energy storage system coupled with a heat pump for different locations and thus different climates in Europe. Through a multi-objective optimization approach applied to the six European geoclusters and applying different solution selection criteria, it was possible to obtain the optimal photovoltaic nominal power (kWp) normalized over the thermal consumption of a reference building and the optimal capacity of the battery per kWp of photovoltaic (kWh:kWp) installed. Due to the normalization process, results can be generalized and can be used for designing similar systems in all buildings around Europe. The results of this work must be intended as a support for designers for the early-design phase of such systems or as an initial guess for an iterative process in more advanced evaluations.

1 INTRODUCTION

One of the main objectives of the European Union is the energy transition to a clean and low-carbon energy system. The building sector is one of the main areas where the decarbonization process should focus, accounting for 28% of energy-related emissions in 2019 [1]. In recent years, the adoption of heat pumps (HP) to cover the heating and cooling demand of buildings has opened a range of opportunities related to sector-coupling. At the same time, the reducing costs of rooftop photovoltaics (PV) and electric storage technologies (BESS) [2], the new national regulations for the adoption of clean energy sources in buildings and the European Climate Target Plan (55% emission reduction with respect to 1990 levels by 2030, first step to achieve carbon neutrality by 2050) make the installation of new photovoltaic system necessary [3] and the coupling of photovoltaic, electric storage and heat pumps more and more attractive. Heat pumps have a great potential to participate to the decarbonization of the heating and cooling sectors since they consume electricity to cover the thermal needs of buildings [4]. More importantly, the electricity consumed can be locally produced by a photovoltaic system. To summarize, there are multiple advantages to couple a heat pump with a photovoltaic system:

- the heat pump can consume the electricity produced by the photovoltaic system, decreasing the carbon footprint of the building
- the heat pump can improve self-consumption, since the thermal load is covered consuming electricity, rather than other sources (natural gas, etc.)
- the heat pump can be controlled by a smart controller shifting part of the electricity demand and further improving self-consumption by consuming the excess electricity that is not directly consumed or stored in the battery

On the other side, heat pumps have a strong impact on the electricity consumption of buildings (in Northern Italy can also double the electricity consumption). For this reason, the design of the coupled photovoltaic plus battery system should account of such additional consumption. The options currently available for designers are mainly two:

- Designing the photovoltaic system to produce the electricity yearly consumed (or use the same methodology on a specific season, e.g. winter). This approach can lead to oversized systems, if

net-billing or net-metering tariff schemes are not available [5]

- Modelling the building, the heating system and the photovoltaic system (e.g. with TRNSYS [6]). This approach is accurate but usually in the early-stage phase of the design process the data required for a simulation are not available. Moreover, the modelling effort is generally considered too high for the early-stage phase.

The aim of this work is to answer to the need of a simple method to be used as a “Go/No-go” decision making support and to provide a simple guide for the early-design stage of photovoltaic plus battery energy storage system coupled with a heat pump for different locations and climates in Europe.

2 METHODOLOGY

In this chapter, the process used to obtain the results is explained in detail. The fundamental steps of the process are the following:

- selection of the reference locations
- selection of a reference building
- simulation of the thermal needs and the electric consumption profile
- optimization of the photovoltaic plus battery system
- solution selection
- normalization of the results

2.1 Geoclusters and reference locations

Considering that the local weather strongly impacts the heat pump consumption profile, Europe was divided in six geoclusters according to the classification reported in [7] (for the Northern geoclusters, Helsinki was used instead of Oslo, due to lack of data). For each geocluster, the typical meteorological year was used to obtain the thermal needs of the reference building (see next section) and for the simulation of the photovoltaic system. The geoclusters and the reference locations are summarized in Table I.

Table I: Geoclusters

Geocluster	Location
Northern	Helsinki
North-East	Warsaw
East	Budapest

Continental Central	Amsterdam
Mediterranean	Barcelona
Atlantic	Dublin

2.2 Reference building

A five-dwellings multi-family house was selected as the reference building for this study. It was assumed that the building is well insulated, according to the recommendation for the installation of heat pumps. It was also assumed that the roof of the reference building is optimally oriented and tilted. Thus, for each location, the optimal orientation and tilt angle of the surfaces available for PV installation were calculated with the online tool PVGIS [8]. They are reported in Table II.

Table II: roof tilt and orientation

Geocluster	Orientation [°]	Tilt [°]
Northern	2	44
North-East	-1	38
East	-2	38
Continental Central	-2	39
Mediterranean	0	37
Atlantic	-1	39

2.3 Thermal needs and electric consumption profile

The electric consumption profile is a fundamental input for the optimization of a photovoltaic system, since from the hourly demand it is possible to estimate the direct self-consumption, the electric grid, and the battery contributions. Moreover, the hourly approach unlocks the possibility to perform a detailed economic analysis. As previously introduced, the local weather has a strong impact on the optimal photovoltaic system design, since a heat pump is used to cover the thermal needs of the building. To calculate the electric consumption profile, the EDGE-HP tool introduced in [9] was used for the six geoclusters. The tool, given the building typology, the location, and the annual cumulative demands for heating, cooling and domestic hot water, calculates the hourly thermal needs of the building. Yearly cumulative thermal needs were set according to the calculations performed in the 4RinEU Horizon 2020 project [10]. The hourly electric consumption profile is then calculated using a performance map of a commercially available air-to-water heat pump. It was also assumed that the heat pump is smart enough to shift half of the night load to daytime to improve self-consumption. This assumption was done since many commercially available heat pumps are already set up to interact with a photovoltaic system.

2.4 Optimization of the photovoltaic plus battery system

The electricity load profiles obtained were used as input for an optimization process (implemented with pymoo [11]) which gives as a result the optimal photovoltaic nominal power (assuming an optimal tilt and orientation) and the optimal battery capacity of the PV+BESS system to be coupled with the heat pump. To obtain the optimal configuration of the PV+BESS+HP system, a multi-objectives optimization algorithm (NSGA-II [12]) implemented in Python was used (the tool was developed within the Horizon 2020 INFINITE project [13]). For each location, the parameters of the optimization are the

photovoltaic system nominal power installed assuming an optimal orientation of the roof and the battery capacity.

The objectives used for the optimization are the maximization of the self-sufficiency (the percentage of the self-consumed energy over the total electricity consumption) and the minimization of the initial costs. The objective functions were calculated according to the following formulas:

- Minimization of the initial costs C_0 of the PV+BESS system calculated as the sum of the initial costs related to the photovoltaic system and the electric battery:

$$C_0 = C_{0,PV} + C_{0,BESS} = P_n * c_{PV} + Q_0 * c_{BESS}$$

where P_n is the photovoltaic system nominal power in kWp, c_{PV} is the unit cost of the photovoltaic system including inverter, cabling, mounting structure, etc. expressed in €/kWp, Q_0 is the battery capacity and c_{BESS} is the unit cost for the battery in €/kWh.

- Maximization of self-sufficiency (SS), calculated with an hourly time step according to the following formula:

$$SS = \frac{\sum_i E_{self,i}}{\sum_i E_{cons,i}}$$

where $E_{self,i}$ is the energy self-consumed at the time step i (directly self-consumed from the photovoltaic system or from the battery) and $E_{cons,i}$ is the energy consumption at the time step i .

During the optimization process, the tool:

- simulates with an hourly time-step the yearly power generation of the photovoltaic system using a simplified irradiance-to-power model (weather data used typical meteorological year file) represented by the following formula:

$$P_i = PR * \eta * A * I_i * (1 - \gamma(T_{mod,i} - T_{ref}))$$

where PR is the performance ratio of the system, η is the module efficiency, A is the module area, I_i is the plane-of-array irradiance calculated from the irradiance components included in the weather file with the Python library pvlib-python [14], γ is the temperature coefficient for power, T_{mod} is the module temperature calculated according to the formula presented in [15] and considering a Ross coefficient equal to 0.0342 K m²/W and T_{ref} is equal to 25°C.

- Simulates the PV+BESS system calculating the energy flows between the PV system, the grid, the battery, and the heat pump to calculate the self-consumed energy. The battery model is based on an energy balance as in [16]
- Calculates the optimization objectives: the self-sufficiency index (SS) and the initial costs

- Repeats the process until the termination criteria is achieved (maximum number of generation)

The result of the optimization process is a set of optimal non-dominated solutions (Pareto front) which represent the solutions with an optimum balance between the two objectives.

2.5 Solution selection

At the end of the optimization process the tool provides a set of optimal solution (Pareto front). For selecting the final solutions, the CO₂ equivalent lifetime emissions and the Net Present Value were calculated.

The CO₂ equivalent lifetime emissions were calculated with the following formula:

$$Em_{CO_2,eq} = em_{PV} * P_{n,PV} + em_{BESS} * Q_{BESS} + em_{grid} * E_{grid}$$

where em_{PV} (kgCO_{2,eq}/kWp) are the specific emissions per kWp for the photovoltaic system accounting of module production, installation, transport, etc., em_{BESS} (kgCO_{2,eq}/kWh) are the specific emissions per unit capacity related to battery production, $P_{n,PV}$ (kWp) is the photovoltaic system nominal power, Q_{BESS} (kWh) is the battery capacity, em_{grid} is the country-dependent emission factor of the grid (kgCO_{2,eq}/kWh) and E_{grid} (kWh) is the estimated lifetime energy purchased from the grid. Once the total emissions $Em_{CO_2,eq}$ (kgCO_{2,eq}) are known, they are normalized over the total electricity consumption to calculate the specific emissions of the PV+BESS+HP system. The resulting value is compared to the emission factor of the country in 1990 [17]. Solutions that do not respect the target of 55% emission reduction with respect to 1990 levels were discarded (red points in Figure 1). Note that, for calculating the specific emissions, the energy consumption is considered. It differs from standard approaches, which usually take into account the overall generation. In this case, the authors decided to change perspective to suggest systems that guarantee the emission reduction requirement by their own, without relying on other possible consumers or on the grid. Considering the actual status, this assumption underestimates the real emissions reduction. In fact, in 2022 the clean energy sent to the grid will be consumed by other consumers and thus would contribute to the overall emission reduction. However, it could be that in future part of the energy produced would be curtailed to guarantee grid stability.

The Net Present Value was calculated for each Pareto-solution according to the model reported in [16]. The formula used is:

$$NPV = -C_0 + \sum_0^N \frac{el_p * \sum E_{self} - \omega_{PV} * P_{n,PV} - C_{BESS}(i) * Q_{BESS}}{(1+i)^t}$$

where el_p is the grid electricity price, E_{self} is the energy self-consumed (used to calculate the savings), ω_{PV} is the yearly cost for maintenance per kWp, $C_{BESS}(i)$ is the cost for the battery replacement at the year i assuming that it must be replaced after 2700 cycles, i is the year and t is the discount rate.

Finally, between the remaining solutions which guarantees the 55% emission reductions with respect to 1990 levels, the cheapest one (lowest initial costs, blue point in Figure

1), the one corresponding to the minimum specific emissions per kWh consumed (orange point in Figure 1) and the one which guarantees the maximum Net Present Value are selected for the normalization process discussed in the following section.

2.6 Normalization of the results

Since the aim of this work is to provide a guide/rule of thumb for the design of PV+BESS (Photovoltaic and battery energy storage system) systems around Europe to be coupled with heat pumps (HP), results were normalized to extend their applicability. They were presented in terms of optimal photovoltaic system nominal power per unit of energy consumed for covering the thermal needs for heating, cooling, and domestic hot water (DHW) preparation (kWp/MWh) and in terms of battery capacity per photovoltaic nominal power (kWh/kWp).

Thus, for each geocluster, results were normalized to calculate the optimal ratio between the PV nominal power (kWp) and the thermal needs of the building (MWh_{th}), and the battery capacity (kWh) over the PV nominal power (kWp) to generalize the output of this work. The process was repeated for all the geoclusters to obtain the results for the European area.

3 RESULTS

In this section the results obtained were reported. Assumptions and data used for the calculations were summarized in Table III.

Table III: data used for calculations

Description	Value	Unit	Reference
cpv	1170	€/kWp	[2]
cbess	563.4	€/kWh	[18]
PR	82	%	[2]
η	20	%	author
A	1.6	m ²	author
γ	-0.47	%/°C	[19]
empv	1010	kgCO _{2,eq} /kWp	[20]
embess	110	kgCO _{2,eq} /kWh	[21]
emgrid	Country-dependent	kgCO _{2,eq} /kWh	[22]
Lifetime	25	years	author
el_p	Country-dependent	€/kWh	[23]
ω_{PV}	30	€/kWp/year	[24]
C_{BESS}	Year-dependent	€/kWh	[18]
Discount rate	3	%	author

As an example, Figure 1 represents the results obtained from the optimization process for the Mediterranean geocluster. Red points correspond to the solution discarded since they could not guarantee the 55% emissions reduction with respect to 1990 levels. The blue point corresponds to the cheapest solution that satisfies the threshold, the yellow point represents the solution with the maximum Net Present Value, while the orange point corresponds to the solution with the minimum lifetime emissions.

Figure 1: solutions obtained for the Mediterranean geocluster

Figure 2: solutions obtained for the East geocluster

Figure 2 represents the results obtained for the East geocluster. With respect to the ones represented in Figure 1, it is possible to notice that undersized systems (low SS) are discarded since they cannot achieve the required emission reduction. On the other hand, also oversized systems are discarded, since achieving high levels of SS requires the installation of an oversized system, connected to high emissions to manufacture the components. Moreover, mainly due to the weather conditions, the solution with minimum costs and the one with the maximum Net Present Value are the same.

The following tables reports the normalized results obtained for each geocluster. Table IV refers to the results obtained selecting the solution with the lowest initial costs, while Table V reports the solutions selected based on the minimum lifetime emissions criteria and Table IV reports solutions based on the maximum Net Present Value criteria.

Table IV: normalized results selected based on the minimum initial costs criteria

Geocluster	PV [kWp/MWh _{th}]	BESS [kWh/kWp]
Northern	0	0
North-East	0.23	0.93
East	0.09	0.65
Continental Central	0.28	1.47
Mediterranean	0.04	0
Atlantic	0	0

Table V: normalized results selected based on the minimum lifetime emissions criteria

Geocluster	PV [kWp/MWh _{th}]	BESS [kWh/kWp]
Northern	0.04	0
North-East	1.80	0.93

East	0.66	1.73
Continental Central	0.92	1.34
Mediterranean	0.64	2.55
Atlantic	0.93	1.85

Table VI: normalized results selected based on the maximum Net Present Value criteria

Geocluster	PV [kWp/MWh _{th}]	BESS [kWh/kWp]
Northern	0.04	0
North-East	0.03	0
East	0.04	0
Continental Central	0.06	0
Mediterranean	0.24	1.67
Atlantic	0.11	0

4 DISCUSSION

Results shown in the previous section open several points of discussion. Firstly, it is possible to notice that results may sensibly vary comparing different geoclusters, mainly due to the strong impact of the climates on the heat-pump seasonal consumptions and the photovoltaic generation. Moreover, the grid emission factor of the countries analyzed has a relevant impact on the solution selection process. For the Northern and Atlantic geoclusters, the actual grid emission factor is already 55% lower than the 1990 value. This means that the photovoltaic system is not required to achieve the decarbonization target and the cheapest solution is to power the heat pump with the national grid electricity. However, if the optimization target is to minimize the lifetime emissions, the installation of a photovoltaic system is recommended for each geocluster. This is also valid for the selection based on the maximization of the Net Present Value of the investment related to the installation of the PV+BESS system. For all geoclusters, the installation of a photovoltaic system is recommended. From Table VI, it is possible to notice that the results obtained for the Mediterranean geoclusters are sensibly different from the others. This is caused by the fact that in the Mediterranean region also in summer the heat pump consumes a relevant quantity of electric energy to cover the cooling demand. The summer consumption coincides with the peak of photovoltaic generation favoring the matching between consumption and generation. Moreover, in the Mediterranean geocluster the photovoltaic generation contributes to cover the winter electricity demand, while for the other geoclusters its impact is marginal in winter. This aspect has a strong impact also on the battery capacity suggested, that for the other geoclusters is 0. This can be explained by the fact that the modest winter production is almost directly self-consumed by the heat-pump and thus reducing the need of an energy storage, while in summer the demand is low or absent. Based on the modest systems suggested in Table VI, with the exception for the Mediterranean geocluster, it is possible to conclude that from an economic perspective the photovoltaic system should be designed accounting mainly of other consumptions (electric vehicle, domestic appliances, etc.) while the heat-pump can only marginally improve the economic outcome. On the contrary, for the Mediterranean geocluster the heat pump should be always considered since it has a strong impact on the final system configuration. According to the results reported in Table V and selected with the minimum emission criteria, it is

possible to conclude that there is a wide space for improvements with respect to the use of the grid electricity to drive the heat pumps regarding lifetime emissions and that both the photovoltaic and battery systems can contribute to the environmental impact reduction.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper aims to provide a rule of thumb for the preliminary design of photovoltaic and electric storage systems coupled with a heat pump for different European climates. The methodology applied is made of three steps: a multi-objective optimization, a normalization process, and a filtering action. The optimization suggests optimal configurations of photovoltaic plus battery systems for a set of reference buildings, considering both economic and energy aspects since the early design phase. The normalization process, transforming the results in terms of photovoltaic nominal power per unit of thermal energy consumed ($\text{kWp/MWh}_{\text{th}}$) and battery capacity per photovoltaic nominal power (kWh/kWp), allows to generalize them. The filtering step, based on the environmental target, helps to make the results valid suggestions considering both the economic and environmental aspects of sustainability. The main relevance of this work is that designers can use the results to find suitable solutions easily and quickly for the design of any photovoltaic plus battery system coupled with a heat pump in the building sector around Europe once the yearly cumulative thermal demand of the building is known. Finally, it must be noted that results of this work consider only the electric consumption profile of a heat pump for suggesting the size of the photovoltaic and battery system.

6 FUTURE WORK

Results presented in this work are based on several assumptions. In future it will be interesting to analyze the impact of such assumptions on the results. In particular, the emissions factor used refers to the actual status (current energy mixes, components production in China, etc.). Such assumptions have an impact on the results as highlighted in [25] and their effect must be analyzed in detail. Possible future changes in the energy mixes and in the cost of the components should also be included in further analysis. Moreover, it will be necessary to go from geocluster to country level to improve the accuracy of the results.

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